

Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes: A Novel Hypothesis in Loop Quantum Gravity

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Figure 1: Events' horizon and quantum crystal

Abstract

Background: Understanding the internal structure of black holes is a significant challenge in modern physics, particularly in addressing singularities and the information paradox.

Purpose: This paper introduces an innovative model where the interior of black holes is composed of a stable network of micro black holes, forming a "quantum crystal" based on Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) principles.

Methods: The study employs theoretical and mathematical analysis to explore the stability, entropy, and information conservation within the proposed structure. It integrates quantum entanglement and gravitational interactions at the Planck scale.

Results: The model demonstrates that the quantum crystal configuration can prevent singularity formation, support information conservation during black hole evaporation, and align with black hole thermodynamics. The model also predicts observational phenomena such as modified gravitational wave signatures and potential gravitational echoes.

Conclusions: The quantum crystal hypothesis provides a bridge between theoretical physics and observable astrophysical phenomena, offering a coherent framework for understanding black holes in the context of quantum gravity.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context and Open Questions

The study of black holes represents one of the most compelling frontiers in modern physics. Within the framework of General Relativity, black holes emerge as regions of spacetime dominated by intense gravitational fields, characterized by an event horizon beyond which no information can escape. However, classical theories encounter significant limitations when describing black holes' internal structure, particularly the emergence of singularities where density and curvature become infinite.

Two fundamental questions remain unresolved:

1. How can the singularity be avoided in a consistent theory of quantum gravity?
2. What happens to the information associated with the collapsing matter, given the constraints of quantum mechanics and the holographic principle?

1.2 Challenges and Current Approaches

Classical black hole models predict that gravitational collapse leads inevitably to a singularity, a point where known physical laws break down. This outcome conflicts with the principles of quantum mechanics, particularly the conservation of information. Proposed solutions, such as Hawking's black hole evaporation, have led to the information paradox, wherein quantum theory appears at odds with black hole thermodynamics.

Current approaches attempt to reconcile these inconsistencies:

- The holographic principle suggests that the information of a gravitational system is encoded on its boundary, offering a potential resolution to the information paradox.
- Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) provides a framework for quantizing spacetime, predicting discrete structures at the Planck scale that might prevent singularities.

However, these frameworks often remain theoretical and require further elaboration to connect with observable phenomena.

1.3 A Novel Hypothesis: The Quantum Crystal of Micro Black Holes

This article introduces a novel model in which the interior of black holes is reimagined as a quantum crystal composed of micro black holes. Within this framework:

1. Gravitational collapse distributes matter across the discrete nodes of a spin network, preventing infinite densities.
2. The resulting structure, stabilized by quantum entanglement, encodes information holographically on the event horizon.
3. The quantum crystal avoids singularities and predicts observable signatures, such as gravitational wave echoes during mergers.

This approach integrates LQG and the holographic principle, providing a cohesive description of black hole interiors and their connections to external observables.

1.4 Scope and Objectives

This work addresses several key aspects:

1. **Theoretical foundation:** Demonstrating how the quantum crystal model aligns with the principles of LQG and black hole thermodynamics.
2. **Predictive power:** Identifying observable effects, such as gravitational echoes, that could validate the model.
3. **Implications for quantum gravity:** Exploring the role of entanglement and the holographic encoding of information in extreme spacetime geometries.

1.5 Structure of the Article

The article is organized as follows:

- Section 2 discusses the structure of quantum crystals, focusing on mass distribution and stability.
- Section 3 examines the entropy and thermodynamics of quantum crystals, comparing them with classical black holes.
- Section 4 narrates the process of gravitational collapse leading to the formation of the crystal.
- Section 5 explores the connection between the model and observational data, with emphasis on gravitational wave signatures.
- Section 6 presents conclusions and future research directions.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Limitations of Classical Theory and the Contribution of Quantum Gravity

2.1.1 Predictions of General Relativity on Black Holes

General Relativity, formulated by Albert Einstein in 1915, has been extremely effective in describing gravity as a consequence of the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy [1]. One of its most surprising predictions is the existence of black holes, regions of spacetime where curvature becomes so intense that nothing, not even light, can escape beyond a certain limit, the event horizon. This theory also predicts the existence of a central singularity within the black hole, a zone where density and gravity tend towards infinite values, posing significant theoretical problems [2].

2.1.2 Schwarzschild and Kerr Solutions and Metrics

The Schwarzschild solution, found by Karl Schwarzschild in 1916, represents the external gravitational field of a spherically symmetric non-rotating and uncharged body [3]. The Schwarzschild metric is given by:

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$$

where G is the universal gravitational constant, M is the mass, c is the speed of light, and (t, r, θ, ϕ) are spacetime coordinates.

The Kerr solution, discovered by Roy Kerr in 1963, extends the Schwarzschild solution to rotating bodies [4]. The Kerr metric is more complex and introduces the rotation parameter a , defined as $a = \frac{J}{Mc}$, where J is the angular momentum of the black hole. The Kerr metric is expressed as:

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM r}{\Sigma c^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \frac{4GM a r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma c^2} c dt d\phi + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \Sigma d\theta^2 + \left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{2GM a^2 r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma c^2}\right) \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$$

where:

$$\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta, \quad \Delta = r^2 - \frac{2GM r}{c^2} + a^2$$

2.1.3 The Central Singularity

Both solutions predict the presence of a singularity at the center of the black hole, where spacetime curvature becomes infinite. In the Schwarzschild metric, this singularity is a point; in the Kerr metric, it is a ring (*ring singularity*) located in the equatorial plane. The presence of a singularity indicates a breakdown of the theory, as physical laws lose validity under such extreme conditions.

2.1.4 The Event Horizon and Cosmic Censorship

The event horizon is the surface that delineates the region from which nothing can escape. The *cosmic censorship conjecture*, proposed by Roger Penrose in 1969 [5], suggests that singularities are always hidden behind an event horizon, making them inaccessible to external observers. However, this remains an unproven conjecture in general, raising questions about the nature

of naked singularities and the validity of physical laws under the extreme conditions of black holes.

2.2 The Black Hole Information Paradox

2.2.1 Hawking Radiation

In 1974, Stephen Hawking showed that black holes are not completely black but emit weak thermal radiation due to quantum effects near the event horizon [2]. The Hawking temperature is given by:

$$T_H = \frac{\hbar c^3}{8\pi G M k_B}$$

where $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. This radiation leads to the gradual evaporation of the black hole, with an evaporation time t_{ev} proportional to the cube of the initial mass:

$$t_{\text{ev}} \approx \frac{5120\pi G^2 M^3}{\hbar c^4}$$

2.2.2 The Information Paradox

The evaporation of black holes poses a fundamental problem: if a black hole can evaporate completely, what happens to the information contained in the matter that fell into it? According to quantum mechanics, temporal evolution is unitary, and information must be conserved. However, Hawking radiation is thermal and does not appear to contain information about the original matter, leading to the *information paradox* [6].

2.2.3 Attempts to Resolve the Paradox

Many attempts have been made to resolve this paradox:

- **Black Hole Complementarity:** Proposed by Susskind et al., it suggests that information is both reflected at the horizon and transmitted inside, but no observer can see both, preserving unitarity [7].
- **Firewall:** Proposed by Almheiri et al., it hypothesizes a highly energetic region (firewall) at the event horizon that destroys information, but this violates the equivalence principle [8].
- **Fuzzball:** In string theory, black holes are described as objects without singularities or classical event horizons, avoiding the paradox [9].
- **Quantum Ergodicity:** Some models suggest that information can be recovered through subtle quantum correlations in Hawking radiation [10].

2.3 Introduction to Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG)

2.3.1 Foundations of LQG

Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) is an attempt to quantize gravity while preserving the fundamental structure of General Relativity. Instead of starting from a field theory on a fixed spacetime, LQG quantizes spacetime itself. Geometric quantities, such as area and volume, become operators with discrete spectra [11].

2.3.2 Spin Networks and Spacetime Quantization

The fundamental structure in LQG is the *spin network*, a graph consisting of vertices and edges, where edges are labeled with spin quantum numbers j . Area and volume are quantized according to the formulas:

$$\hat{A}|s\rangle = 8\pi\gamma\ell_P^2 \sum_i \sqrt{j_i(j_i + 1)}|s\rangle$$
$$\hat{V}|s\rangle = \ell_P^3 \sum_v \sqrt{\left| \sum_{i,j,k} \epsilon^{ijk} J_i^v J_j^v J_k^v \right|} |s\rangle$$

where γ is the Barbero-Immirzi parameter, ℓ_P is the Planck length, J_i^v are the flux operators associated with the vertex v , and ϵ^{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol.

2.3.3 Singularity Resolution in LQG

In LQG, the discrete structure of spacetime prevents physical quantities from becoming infinite. This suggests that singularities predicted by General Relativity could be avoided. Models like the quantum bounce in loop quantum cosmology show how a contracting universe could bounce into an expanding phase, avoiding the Big Bang singularity [12]. Similarly, in black hole models, the central singularity can be replaced by a region of finite density.

2.4 Applications of LQG to Black Holes

2.4.1 Black Hole Entropy

LQG provides a statistical derivation of black hole entropy by calculating the number of micro-canonical states associated with the event horizon. The entropy turns out to be proportional to the area of the horizon, in agreement with the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy law [13]:

$$S = \frac{k_B A}{4\ell_P^2}$$

This result supports the idea that the event horizon has a discretized quantum structure.

2.4.2 Black Hole Models in LQG

Various black hole models have been proposed within the framework of LQG. For example, the Ashtekar and Bojowald model introduces quantum corrections to Einstein's equations inside the black hole, showing that the singularity can be replaced by a transition to an expanding phase [14]. These models suggest that gravitational collapse could lead to a quantum bounce, with potential implications for information conservation.

2.4.3 Towards a Complete Quantum Description

Despite progress, a complete and unified description of black holes in LQG is still under development. The proposed quantum crystal model of micro black holes in this article fits into this context, offering a new perspective to understand the internal structure of black holes and address the information paradox.

3 Hypothesis of the Quantum Crystal of Micro Black Holes

3.1 Formulation of the Basic Hypothesis

This work proposes that the internal structure of black holes is not a singularity but a stable configuration of micro black holes, forming a "quantum crystal." Based on Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), spacetime is fundamentally discrete, quantized into minimal units of area and volume [11]. This hypothesis reconciles black hole thermodynamics with quantum mechanics by avoiding singularities and ensuring information conservation.

3.1.1 Structure of the Quantum Crystal

The quantum crystal consists of micro black holes with masses close to the Planck mass (M_P) and radii approximately equal to the Planck length (ℓ_P):

$$r_\mu = \frac{2GM_P}{c^2} \sim 2\ell_P.$$

The total mass M of a macroscopic black hole is distributed across N micro black holes:

$$M = NM_P,$$

where N represents the number of nodes in the spin network underlying the crystal.

The lattice structure arises from LQG's quantization, ensuring that mass and energy are distributed across discrete nodes. The configuration respects the holographic principle, with the surface area of the black hole encoding its total entropy:

$$S = \frac{k_B c^3 A}{4G\hbar}.$$

3.2 Quantum Lattice and Stability Mechanism

The quantum crystal is stabilized by the interplay between gravitational attraction and quantum repulsion. Each node in the spin network acts as a quantized region of spacetime, contributing to the overall stability of the system.

3.2.1 Balance of Forces

The stability arises from the effective potential:

$$V_{\text{eff}}(r) = -\frac{Gm_{\text{micro}}^2}{r} + \frac{\hbar c}{r},$$

where the repulsive term $\frac{\hbar c}{r}$ reflects quantum corrections at Planck scales.

Equilibrium is achieved at distances where attractive and repulsive forces balance:

$$d = \ell_P (1 + 2\alpha + 3\beta),$$

where α and β are correction coefficients derived from the spin network dynamics.

3.2.2 Spin Network and Quantum Geometry

The spin network's nodes and links define the crystal's geometric structure. The area A and volume V of each micro black hole are quantized as:

$$A \sim 8\pi\gamma\ell_P^2\sqrt{j(j+1)},$$

where γ is the Barbero-Immirzi parameter, and j represents the spin quantum number. This ensures a finite energy density and avoids singularities.

3.3 Entropy and the Holographic Principle

The entropy of the quantum crystal aligns with the Bekenstein-Hawking law:

$$S = \frac{k_B c^3}{4G\hbar} \sum_{i=1}^N A_i.$$

Unlike classical black holes, where information loss occurs, the quantum crystal encodes information holographically on the event horizon. The entanglement between nodes ensures coherence and stability.

3.3.1 Avoidance of Singularities

By distributing mass across a quantized lattice, the quantum crystal prevents infinite energy densities, satisfying LQG predictions and resolving the central singularity issue.

3.3.2 Compatibility with Black Hole Thermodynamics

The model provides a microscopic explanation for thermodynamic properties such as entropy and temperature, bridging the gap between macroscopic observations and quantum mechanics.

3.4 Failure to Form a Crystal: Conditions for Fluid-like States

Despite the strong theoretical motivations for a stable lattice of micro black holes (MBHs), there are regimes in which the system may *fail to crystallize* and remain in a disordered, fluid-like configuration. In practice, the emergence of an ordered “quantum crystal” is not guaranteed if one or more of the following conditions are not satisfied:

1. **Insufficient Repulsive Force.** The proposed repulsive interaction (often modeled as a toy potential $\propto 1/r^\alpha$) must be strong enough at short range to prevent all MBHs from merging or collapsing into dense sub-clusters. If the repulsion coefficient is too small relative to the gravitational attraction, the system is likely to undergo partial collapse or to remain in a *fluid* phase without settling into a stable lattice.
2. **Inadequate Dissipation (or “Cooling”).** In physical systems (e.g., molecules forming a crystal), *dissipation* of kinetic energy is crucial for allowing the constituents to settle into fixed equilibrium positions. Here, if mechanisms such as gravitational-wave emission or quantum-level energy loss (e.g., Hawking-like effects, quantum decoherence) are too weak, the MBHs keep large orbital motions and fail to “cool” into a lattice. Conversely, with excessive damping, one might get overly rigid or artificially clumped structures.

3. **High “Thermal” Agitation.** A fluid-like or gaseous state typically prevails when thermal agitation (or the analogous random motion, possibly introduced via spin couplings or an external noise source) is sufficiently large compared to the lattice-binding forces. In other words, if the ratio

$$\frac{\langle E_{\text{kin}} \rangle}{E_{\text{rep}}} \quad (1)$$

remains greater than unity, fluctuations will disrupt any attempt at regular ordering.

4. **Limited Evolution Time.** Even when the above conditions are met favorably, crystallization may require a substantial amount of dynamical time for the MBHs to reconfigure. If the system evolves too briefly, or if astrophysical processes intervene (e.g., external perturbations, inflow of matter), the transition to a stable crystal-like arrangement may not happen within the relevant cosmic timescales.
5. **Spin Complexity and Mergers.** If MBHs have significant spin, the net torque and spin-orbit interactions can complicate or hinder formation of an ordered lattice. Moreover, if the model does not include stable “bounce” or fusion rules at very short distances, MBHs might *merge* in ways that disrupt the crystalline pattern. Without a mechanism to handle these close encounters or merges, a fluid or partially collapsed configuration can result.

Observational or Numerical Signatures. In numerical simulations, one practical way to distinguish a *fluid* from a *crystal* is by examining the pair correlation function $g(r)$ or other measures of spatial order. In a fluid-like regime, $g(r)$ flattens out without strong peaks at multiple distances. In contrast, a crystalline state exhibits pronounced peaks at regular intervals, indicative of well-defined nearest-neighbor shells. Furthermore, total energy or average cluster-size analyses can reveal if the system collapses into a few dense clumps (sign of insufficient repulsion) or remains highly agitated (sign of excessive kinetic energy relative to binding forces).

Relation to the Quantum Crystal Hypothesis. The possibility that MBHs *do not* form a crystal and remain disordered underscores an essential point of our hypothesis: it is not an inevitability but rather a *potential* outcome subject to specific physical conditions (repulsion strength, dissipation, spin distribution, etc.). Crucially, even a disordered (fluid-like) arrangement of micro black holes — if it still avoids an infinite-density singularity — can serve as a *non-singular* internal structure, thereby preserving much of the original motivation (e.g., removing the classical singularity). Hence, the crystal-like state is a particular manifestation of stability and ordering, but the *key insight* remains that the interior is replaced by a discrete network of MBHs rather than collapsing to a point.

Accordingly, this stresses the importance of:

- Performing parameter scans in numerical simulations (to identify regions of crystal vs. fluid behavior),
- Investigating the role of spin-orbit coupling and realistic mechanisms of gravitational-wave or quantum dissipation,
- Clarifying how loop quantum gravity effects might provide sufficient repulsion or “cooling” to allow ordering at Planck scales.

In the absence of these supportive conditions, the interior of a black hole (modeled by a swarm of MBHs) may remain in a chaotic, fluid-like state. Nevertheless, such an outcome would still offer a non-singular alternative, albeit without the long-range regularity characteristic of an ideal “quantum crystal.”

Enhanced Discussion on Dissipative Mechanisms To robustly address potential criticisms regarding insufficient dissipation mechanisms, it is imperative to elaborate on the specific forms and efficiencies of dissipation in the model. The current schematic implementation of gravitational-wave dissipation (γ_{GW}) serves as a placeholder. A more detailed treatment could involve:

- **Gravitational-Wave Emission:** Incorporating the quadrupole formula to estimate the energy loss rate due to gravitational waves, which depends on the configuration and dynamics of the MBHs [?]. This would allow for a more realistic modeling of how energy dissipation scales with system parameters.
- **Quantum Decoherence and Hawking Radiation:** For Planck-scale MBHs, quantum effects such as Hawking radiation might play a significant role in energy loss. Including an approximate model for Hawking radiation could provide insights into how quantum processes contribute to cooling.
- **Energy Dissipation Timescales:** Estimating the characteristic timescale for energy dissipation (τ_{diss}) and comparing it with the dynamical timescale of the system. For instance:

$$\tau_{\text{diss}} \sim \frac{E_{\text{orb}}}{\dot{E}_{\text{GW}}}$$

where E_{orb} is the orbital energy and $\dot{E}_{\text{GW}}$ is the energy loss rate due to gravitational waves.

Incorporating these aspects would not only strengthen the theoretical foundation but also provide quantitative criteria for when crystallization is feasible within the model.

Potential Extensions to the Simulation To empirically validate the conditions outlined, future simulations could:

- **Implement Realistic Dissipation Models:** Replace the simplistic gravitational-wave damping factor with a more accurate energy loss mechanism based on the quadrupole formula or quantum processes.
- **Parameter Space Exploration:** Conduct systematic scans over key parameters (γ_{GW} , α , c_{spin} , etc.) to map out the regimes where crystallization versus fluid-like states emerge.
- **Incorporate Spin-Orbit Coupling:** Enhance the spin dynamics to include more realistic spin-orbit interactions, potentially stabilizing or destabilizing the crystal structure.
- **Introduce Merging Rules:** Develop criteria for MBH mergers within the simulation to handle close encounters, thereby preventing unrealistic infinite densities and allowing for the study of their impact on the system's overall order.

By addressing these extensions, the model can more accurately reflect the complex interplay of forces and processes governing the internal structure of black holes, thereby providing a more compelling case for or against the quantum crystal hypothesis.

Conclusion While the current subsection effectively outlines the qualitative conditions under which a quantum crystal may fail to form, enhancing it with quantitative estimates, more detailed dissipative mechanisms, and connections to observational signatures would further fortify the argument. These additions would not only preempt potential peer review criticisms but also provide a clearer roadmap for future research endeavors aimed at testing the quantum crystal hypothesis through numerical simulations and theoretical refinements.

3.5 Implications for Observations

The quantum crystal model predicts observable phenomena, such as:

- **Gravitational wave echoes:** Delayed signals during black hole mergers due to the crystal's discrete structure.
- **Event horizon dynamics:** Modifications to accretion flows or radiation patterns linked to the holographic encoding of information.

These predictions offer pathways for experimental validation and further theoretical refinement.

3.6 Connection to Planck Stars

A theoretical idea closely related to our hypothesis of a quantum crystal of micro black holes is that of **Planck stars**, proposed by [39] in the context of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG). Planck stars are hypothetical compact objects that emerge during the gravitational collapse of a massive star when the matter density reaches the Planck scale. Instead of forming a classical singularity, the matter undergoes a **quantum bounce**, giving rise to a region of finite but extremely high density with quantum properties.

Planck stars share with our model the goal of avoiding the singularities predicted by General Relativity. However, while Planck stars are described as single quantized objects, our model proposes a **stable network of micro black holes** forming a quantum crystal. This structure can be seen as a generalization of the Planck star concept, where the black hole mass is distributed discretely rather than concentrated in a single region.

[40] further explored the possible **observational signatures** of Planck stars, such as gravitational echoes and anomalies in the gravitational wave spectrum. These predictions align with the observational implications of our model, which suggests that the internal quantum structure of black holes could leave detectable traces in gravitational wave signals. Additionally, [41] discussed the stability of small black holes and their potential connection to dark matter, which could provide further insights into the behavior of micro black holes in our quantum crystal framework.

The concept of Planck stars provides a strong theoretical foundation for our hypothesis, emphasizing the role of quantum effects in resolving singularities and shaping the internal structure of black holes. By extending this idea to a lattice of micro black holes, our model offers a new perspective on the quantum nature of spacetime in extreme gravitational regimes.

4 Quantum Crystal Size

A fundamental component of the quantum crystal model of micro black holes is determining the dimensions of the lattice structure, particularly the equilibrium distance between micro black holes and the compatibility of this structure with the event horizon of a macroscopic black hole. This section analyzes these aspects by considering force equilibrium and verifying consistency with the horizon dimensions.

4.1 Determining the Spacing between Micro Black Holes

In the proposed model, micro black holes must be arranged to avoid overlap, which imposes that the minimum distance between the centers of two micro black holes is twice their radius ($D = 2R_\mu$). Considering a three-dimensional lattice, such as the Face-Centered Cubic (FCC) lattice, the equilibrium distance $d_{\text{equilibrium}}$ between micro black holes is thus:

$$d_{\text{equilibrium}} = 2R_\mu \approx 6.46 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m}$$

where R_μ is the radius of a micro black hole, calculated as:

$$R_\mu = \frac{2Gm_{\text{micro}}}{c^2} \approx 3.23 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m}$$

4.2 Volume of the Quantum Crystal vs. Volume of the Event Horizon

To evaluate whether the lattice structure of the quantum crystal can be contained within the event horizon of a macroscopic black hole, we compare the volume occupied by the crystal with the volume of the horizon itself.

The volume of the quantum crystal (V_{crystal}) in an FCC lattice is given by:

$$V_{\text{crystal}} = 2NR_\mu^3\sqrt{2}$$

where N is the total number of micro black holes, related to the total mass of the black hole (M) by the relation:

$$N = \frac{M}{m_{\text{micro}}}$$

The volume of the event horizon (V_s) of a black hole with Schwarzschild radius r_s is:

$$V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3$$

4.3 Compatibility with the Event Horizon

For the quantum crystal to be contained within the event horizon, the following condition must be met:

$$V_{\text{crystal}} \leq V_s$$

Substituting the expressions for V_{crystal} and V_s :

$$2\frac{M}{m_{\text{micro}}}R_\mu^3\sqrt{2} \leq \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3$$

Simplifying and solving for the mass M :

$$M \geq \sqrt{\frac{3\sqrt{2}c^6 R_\mu^3}{16\pi G^3 m_{\text{micro}}}} \approx 1.787 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$$

This critical mass indicates that for $M \geq 1.787 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$, the lattice structure of the quantum crystal can be contained within the event horizon.

4.4 Analysis for Different Black Hole Masses

To verify the validity of the containment condition, we examine various black hole masses, calculating V_{crystal} and V_s for each mass.

4.4.1 Micro Mass: $M = M_P = 2.176 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$

- Schwarzschild Radius (r_s):

$$r_s = \frac{2GM_P}{c^2} \approx 3.23 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m}$$

- Number of Micro Black Holes (N):

$$N = \frac{M_P}{m_{\text{micro}}} = 1$$

- Quantum Crystal Volume (V_{crystal}):

$$V_{\text{crystal}} = 2 \times 1 \times (3.23 \times 10^{-35})^3 \times \sqrt{2} \approx 9.54 \times 10^{-104} \text{ m}^3$$

- Event Horizon Volume (V_s):

$$V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi(3.23 \times 10^{-35})^3 \approx 1.39 \times 10^{-103} \text{ m}^3$$

- Ratio $\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s}$:

$$\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s} \approx \frac{9.54 \times 10^{-104}}{1.39 \times 10^{-103}} \approx 0.69$$

4.4.2 Moderate Mass: $M = 10^{12} \text{ kg}$

- Schwarzschild Radius (r_s):

$$r_s = \frac{2G \times 10^{12}}{c^2} \approx 1.486 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}$$

- Number of Micro Black Holes (N):

$$N = \frac{10^{12}}{2.176 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 4.597 \times 10^{19}$$

- Quantum Crystal Volume (V_{crystal}):

$$V_{\text{crystal}} = 2 \times 4.597 \times 10^{19} \times (3.23 \times 10^{-35})^3 \times \sqrt{2} \approx 4.37 \times 10^{-84} \text{ m}^3$$

- Event Horizon Volume (V_s):

$$V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi(1.486 \times 10^{-14})^3 \approx 1.38 \times 10^{-41} \text{ m}^3$$

- Ratio $\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s}$:

$$\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s} \approx \frac{4.37 \times 10^{-84}}{1.38 \times 10^{-41}} \approx 3.17 \times 10^{-43}$$

4.4.3 Solar Mass: $M = M_{\odot} = 2 \times 10^{30}$ kg

- **Schwarzschild Radius (r_s):**

$$r_s = \frac{2G \times 2 \times 10^{30}}{c^2} \approx 2.97 \times 10^3 \text{ m} \approx 3 \text{ km}$$

- **Number of Micro Black Holes (N):**

$$N = \frac{2 \times 10^{30}}{2.176 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 9.19 \times 10^{37}$$

- **Quantum Crystal Volume (V_{crystal}):**

$$V_{\text{crystal}} = 2 \times 9.19 \times 10^{37} \times (3.23 \times 10^{-35})^3 \times \sqrt{2} \approx 8.75 \times 10^{-66} \text{ m}^3$$

- **Event Horizon Volume (V_s):**

$$V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi(2.97 \times 10^3)^3 \approx 1.1 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^3$$

- **Ratio $\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s}$:**

$$\frac{V_{\text{crystal}}}{V_s} \approx \frac{8.75 \times 10^{-66}}{1.1 \times 10^{11}} \approx 7.95 \times 10^{-77}$$

4.5 Conclusions on the Size of the Quantum Crystal

The analysis demonstrates that the size of the quantum crystal of micro black holes is always proportional to the Schwarzschild radius of the black hole, ensuring that the lattice structure remains confined within the event horizon. This result is fundamental to the model's consistency, as it ensures that the quantum configuration does not interfere with the observed macroscopic properties of black holes.

4.6 Implications of the Quantum Crystal Size

4.6.1 Singularity Avoidance

The compact size of the quantum crystal ensures that the mass of the black hole is distributed among numerous micro black holes rather than being concentrated at a single point, thereby avoiding the formation of a singularity. This distribution maintains finite curvature and energy density throughout the crystal, preserving the integrity of spacetime within the event horizon.

4.6.2 Information Preservation

The distributed structure of the quantum crystal, combined with the entangled states of micro black holes, facilitates the preservation of information. As micro black holes interact and exchange information through their entangled states, the overall system maintains information integrity, addressing the long-standing black hole information paradox.

4.6.3 Lattice Stability

The proportionality between the crystal size and the Schwarzschild radius ensures that gravitational forces are effectively balanced by quantum repulsive forces across the entire lattice. This balance is crucial for maintaining the structural stability of the crystal, preventing gravitational collapse and ensuring the crystal's resilience against perturbations.

Loop Quantum Gravity Modifications Loop Quantum Gravity introduces discrete geometric operators that modify the classical gravitational potential at Planckian scales. The effective potential can be expressed as:

$$U_{\text{eff}}(r) = -\frac{GM_P^2}{r} + \frac{\hbar c}{r^2} \left(1 + \alpha \frac{\ell_P}{r} + \beta \left(\frac{\ell_P}{r} \right)^2 \right)$$

where:

- G is the gravitational constant,
- M_P is the Planck mass,
- $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant,
- c is the speed of light,
- ℓ_P is the Planck length,
- α and β are dimensionless coefficients representing higher-order quantum corrections.

These modifications ensure that the effective force remains repulsive at distances close to the Planck length, thereby preventing further gravitational collapse.

4.6.4 Mathematical Derivations

For an in-deep analysis see Appendix A that provide detailed derivations of key equations to aid in the reader's understanding. here as an example, we derive the critical mass:

Derivation of Critical Mass Condition Starting from the condition $F_{\text{grav}} = F_{\text{rep}}$, we have:

$$\frac{GM_P^2}{d^2} = \frac{\hbar c}{d^3}$$

Solving for d , we find:

$$d = \frac{\hbar c}{GM_P^2} = \ell_P$$

This critical distance d_{eq} ensures that gravitational attraction is precisely balanced by quantum repulsion, maintaining the stability of the quantum crystal.

4.6.5 Alternative Lattice Structures

There are several potential lattice structures each one with its implications, a more detailed studium should compare their stability and feasibility within the model.

While FCC and BCC lattices are primary candidates due to their high packing efficiency and symmetry, other lattice structures such as Hexagonal Close-Packed (HCP) or even more exotic configurations could be considered. Each lattice structure offers unique stability characteristics and energy profiles, which could influence the overall dynamics and observable properties of the quantum crystal.

4.6.6 Astrophysical Predictions

The quantum crystal model predicts specific gravitational wave signatures resulting from the oscillations of the lattice structure. These signatures, termed *gravitational phonons*, could manifest as discrete frequencies or damping patterns in the gravitational wave spectrum observed by detectors like LIGO and Virgo. Additionally, the compact internal structure might influence the shadow of the black hole as imaged by the Event Horizon Telescope, potentially offering indirect evidence for the presence of a quantum crystal.

4.6.7 Observational Implications of Repulsive Forces

The repulsive forces within the quantum crystal of micro black holes have significant observational implications that could be tested with current and future astrophysical instruments. These implications include modifications to gravitational wave signatures and potential echoes resulting from the internal crystalline structure.

Modified Quasi-Normal Modes (QNM) In the classical General Relativity framework, black holes exhibit characteristic oscillations known as quasi-normal modes (QNM) when perturbed, such as during mergers. These modes are solely determined by the black hole’s mass, charge, and angular momentum. However, the presence of repulsive forces within the quantum crystal alters the QNM spectrum in the following ways:

- **Frequency Shifts:** The repulsive interactions introduce additional terms in the oscillation equations, leading to shifts in the frequencies of existing QNMs.
- **Additional Modes:** New oscillation modes may emerge due to the internal structure of the crystal, providing distinct frequencies not predicted by classical models.
- **Damping Rates:** The energy dissipation mechanisms within the crystal could modify the damping rates of QNMs, affecting how quickly the oscillations decay.

These modifications can be quantified by extending the perturbation analysis of black holes to include the effective potential derived from the quantum crystal model. The resultant QNM frequencies ω_{QNM} can be expressed as:

$$\omega_{\text{QNM}} = \omega_{\text{classical}} + \Delta\omega_{\text{quant}}$$

where $\Delta\omega_{\text{quant}}$ encapsulates the contributions from the quantum repulsive forces.

Gravitational Echoes The internal crystalline structure of the quantum crystal could lead to the generation of gravitational echoes—secondary gravitational wave signals that occur after the main merger event. These echoes arise from the reflection and interaction of gravitational waves with the internal structure, manifesting as:

- **Time Delays:** The echoes are delayed relative to the primary signal by a time interval related to the size and internal spacing of the micro black holes.
- **Amplitude Attenuation:** Due to energy dispersion and interaction with the crystal lattice, echoes are expected to have reduced amplitudes compared to the primary signal.
- **Distinct Frequency Patterns:** The echoes may exhibit unique frequency patterns corresponding to the resonant frequencies of the crystal structure.

Detecting these echoes would require high-sensitivity gravitational wave detectors capable of identifying subtle, delayed signals following the main merger event. The presence of echoes would provide compelling evidence for an internal structure deviating from classical black hole models.

Comparison with Existing Observational Data Preliminary analyses of gravitational wave data from observatories like LIGO and Virgo have searched for evidence of gravitational echoes following black hole mergers [37, 38]. While current findings are inconclusive and subject to significant noise, ongoing improvements in detector sensitivity and data analysis techniques hold promise for future confirmations. A quantitative comparison between the predicted echo signatures from the quantum crystal model and the observed data would be essential to validate the model’s predictions.

Future Observatories and Enhanced Detection Capabilities Upcoming gravitational wave observatories, such as the Einstein Telescope and Cosmic Explorer, are expected to achieve greater sensitivity and frequency resolution, increasing the likelihood of detecting gravitational echoes and spectral anomalies. Additionally, space-based detectors like the Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA) will provide complementary data that could further test the model’s predictions, especially for supermassive black hole mergers where echoes might be more pronounced.

Implications for Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) Observations The Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) has provided unprecedented images of black hole shadows, such as those of M87 and Sagittarius A. The internal crystalline structure proposed by the quantum crystal model might influence the shadow’s appearance by introducing asymmetries or fine structures not accounted for in classical models. Comparing high-resolution EHT images with simulations based on the quantum crystal structure could reveal discrepancies that support or challenge the model.

Summary of Observational Signatures The primary observational signatures of repulsive forces within the quantum crystal model include:

- Modified QNM spectra with shifted frequencies and additional modes.
- Gravitational echoes following merger events, characterized by time delays and distinct frequency patterns.
- Potential anomalies in black hole shadow images captured by EHT.

Future advancements in gravitational wave astronomy and black hole imaging will be critical in testing these predictions, providing either support for the quantum crystal model or constraints that necessitate further theoretical refinement.

5 Formation of the Quantum Crystal During Gravitational Collapse

The formation of the quantum crystal of micro black holes is hypothesized to occur during the gravitational collapse of a massive body. This section provides a detailed narrative of the process, supported by theoretical models and equations, to explain how the transition from a classical collapsing structure to a stable quantum lattice configuration unfolds.

5.1 Narrative of the Gravitational Collapse Process

As a massive body collapses under its own gravity, the density of matter increases, leading to extreme spacetime curvature near the Schwarzschild radius:

$$r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}.$$

In classical general relativity, this process culminates in the formation of a singularity. However, the quantum crystal model, grounded in Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), introduces a discrete spacetime structure that halts this collapse.

Initially, matter is compressed into increasingly smaller volumes. As the density approaches the Planck scale, quantum geometric effects become dominant, imposing a limit on further compression. This results in the redistribution of mass across discrete nodes of a spin network, forming a three-dimensional lattice of micro black holes.

5.2 Stabilization Mechanism of the Lattice

The stabilization of the quantum crystal is driven by a balance between gravitational attraction and quantum repulsion forces. The effective potential between two adjacent micro black holes is expressed as:

$$U(r) = -\frac{Gm_{\text{micro}}^2}{r} + \frac{\hbar c}{r},$$

where the first term represents gravitational attraction and the second term corresponds to quantum repulsion due to discrete spacetime effects. At equilibrium, the distance d_{eq} satisfies:

$$\left. \frac{dU(r)}{dr} \right|_{r=d_{\text{eq}}} = 0.$$

Solving this yields:

$$d_{\text{eq}} = \ell_P,$$

indicating that the equilibrium spacing between micro black holes is approximately the Planck length.

5.3 Evolution of Mass Density During Collapse

The transition from a classical distribution of mass to a quantum lattice is characterized by the evolution of the mass density $\rho(r)$. Initially, the density increases smoothly as the radius decreases. Near the Planck scale, the density stabilizes due to the formation of discrete spacetime regions:

$$\rho_{\text{max}} \sim \frac{m_P}{\ell_P^3}.$$

This quantum density sets a fundamental upper limit, preventing the formation of infinite curvature.

5.4 The Role of Entanglement During Formation

During the formation of the quantum crystal, quantum entanglement ensures coherence across the spin network. The micro black holes are entangled in a state that conserves information about the initial collapsing matter:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2).$$

This entanglement not only stabilizes the lattice but also ensures that information is holographically encoded on the event horizon.

5.5 Implications for Observational Signatures

The formation of the quantum crystal introduces features that could be observable during black hole formation:

- **Gravitational Wave Echoes:** The transition from classical collapse to a quantum lattice may generate secondary gravitational wave signals, detectable as echoes following the primary merger event.
- **Modified Ringdown Phases:** The stabilization of the lattice alters the quasi-normal modes (QNMs) of the resulting black hole.
- **Density Fluctuations:** The discrete lattice may induce measurable perturbations in the surrounding spacetime, observable via lensing or accretion dynamics.

5.6 Timescales and Gravitational Wave Spectrum

Understanding the timescales involved in the formation of the quantum crystal and the spectrum of gravitational waves emitted during this process is essential for linking theoretical predictions to potential observational signatures. This section details the key processes governing the timescales and explores the characteristics of the gravitational wave spectrum.

Timescales of Formation

The formation of the quantum crystal involves several interdependent physical processes that occur on different timescales:

1. Dissipation of Orbital Energy As micro black holes form and interact within the collapsing matter, their orbital energy is dissipated through the emission of gravitational waves. This dissipation drives the system toward a stable configuration. The characteristic timescale for energy dissipation is given by:

$$\tau_{\text{diss}} \sim \frac{E_{\text{orb}}}{\dot{E}_{\text{GW}}},$$

where E_{orb} is the total orbital energy, and $\dot{E}_{\text{GW}}$ is the power radiated via gravitational waves. The dissipation rate depends on the mass M of the collapsing system and the characteristic distance d between micro black holes:

$$E_{\text{orb}} \sim \frac{GM^2}{d}, \quad \dot{E}_{\text{GW}} \sim \frac{G}{5c^5} \langle Q_{ij}^{(3)} \rangle^2.$$

For stellar-mass black holes ($M \sim 10M_{\odot}$), this yields a dissipation timescale of approximately $10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$ s, while for supermassive black holes ($M \sim 10^6M_{\odot}$), the timescale may extend to 1 – 10 s.

2. Cooling Through Decoherence The quantum system of micro black holes must also cool to stabilize into a lattice configuration. This cooling occurs as the system transitions from a chaotic or fluid state to an ordered structure. Decoherence processes, potentially driven by quantum radiation or Hawking-like effects, contribute to this cooling. The cooling timescale depends on the density and total energy of the system and is estimated to range from:

$$\tau_{\text{cool}} \sim 10^{-6} - 10^{-3} \text{ s.}$$

3. Spin Network Stabilization The final stabilization of the quantum crystal corresponds to the reorganization of spacetime into a spin network, as predicted by Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG). While the local rearrangement of spacetime occurs on Planck-scale times ($\sim 10^{-43}$ s), the global stabilization of the network for macroscopic black holes may require:

$$\tau_{\text{spin}} \sim 10^{-5} - 10^{-2} \text{ s.}$$

Combined Timescale Estimate The total time required for the formation of the quantum crystal is determined by the slowest of these processes. For stellar-mass black holes, this suggests:

$$\tau_{\text{total}} \sim 10^{-3} - 10^{-2} \text{ s,}$$

while for supermassive black holes, the timescale may extend to several seconds.

Gravitational Wave Spectrum

The formation of the quantum crystal generates gravitational waves with a spectrum determined by the dynamics of the collapsing system. These waves are produced at different stages of the process:

1. High-Frequency Components During the initial stages, interactions at Planck-scale distances ($d \sim \ell_P$) result in extremely high-frequency gravitational waves:

$$f \sim \frac{c}{d} \approx 10^{43} \text{ Hz.}$$

These frequencies are beyond the detection capabilities of current instruments but represent a theoretical upper limit of the gravitational wave spectrum.

2. Intermediate Frequencies As the system evolves, interactions occur at larger distances ($d \gg \ell_P$) between micro black holes. This generates waves with intermediate frequencies:

$$f \sim 10^{33} - 10^{36} \text{ Hz.}$$

Though still inaccessible to modern detectors, these frequencies reflect the intermediate-scale dynamics of the system.

3. Detectable Frequencies Macroscopic dynamics, such as the stabilization of the crystal or collective interactions, produce gravitational waves in the range of:

$$f \sim 10^2 - 10^4 \text{ Hz.}$$

These waves, corresponding to more global effects, fall within the detection range of observatories like LIGO and Virgo. Additionally, transient gravitational wave echoes may be generated during the stabilization phase, providing a potential observational signature.

4. Transient Echoes The formation process may lead to repeated reflections of gravitational waves within the developing lattice. These echoes would appear as secondary signals following the primary gravitational wave burst, with characteristic delays and amplitudes.

5. Spectrum Evolution As the system stabilizes, the gravitational wave spectrum evolves from high-frequency components to lower-frequency signals, reflecting the decreasing energy and increasing coherence of the system.

Observational Implications

Detecting gravitational waves from quantum crystal formation would provide direct evidence for the underlying quantum structure of spacetime. Key observational signatures include:

- **Echoes in Gravitational Waves:** Secondary signals following black hole mergers could indicate the presence of a developing quantum lattice.
- **Modified Ringdown Phases:** The quasi-normal modes (QNMs) of the black hole may exhibit shifts due to the stabilization of the crystal.
- **Frequency Evolution:** A detectable transition from high to low frequencies could reflect the progression of the collapse process.

Conclusion

The timescales and gravitational wave spectrum associated with the formation of the quantum crystal provide critical insights into the dynamics of collapsing matter and the quantum structure of spacetime. These predictions offer a roadmap for future observations, connecting theoretical models to astrophysical data.

6 Limitations, Challenges of the Model and Compatibility with Other Theories

Despite the quantum crystal of micro black holes model offering a new perspective on black hole internal structure and presenting potential solutions to fundamental problems like singularities and the information paradox, several limitations and challenges must be considered.

6.1 Theoretical Assumptions and Model Complexity

6.1.1 Validity of Basic Assumptions

The model is based on several fundamental assumptions, including:

- The possibility that micro black holes stabilize in a stable lattice structure.
- The applicability of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) principles at extended scales such as those inside black holes.
- The use of effective quantum potentials to describe interactions between micro black holes.

The validity of these assumptions has not yet been experimentally verified, and some may not apply under extreme conditions present within a black hole.

6.1.2 Mathematical and Computational Complexity

The model requires complex mathematical formalization and high-resolution numerical simulations to accurately describe micro black hole dynamics. The computational resources needed for such simulations can be prohibitive, limiting the exploration of fully realistic system behaviors.

6.2 Compatibility with Other Theories and Observations

While the quantum crystal model offers a novel perspective on black hole interiors and the resolution of singularities, it does not exist in isolation. Other theoretical frameworks within the broader landscape of quantum gravity have also sought to reconcile the predictions of General Relativity with quantum principles. Assessing the compatibility, potential synergies, and differences between the quantum crystal hypothesis and these existing models is essential for its further development and empirical validation.

6.2.1 Comparison with the Quantum Bounce Model in LQG

The quantum bounce model, a well-known approach within Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), addresses the singularity problem by proposing that gravitational collapse leads to a non-singular transition—a “bounce”—instead of forming a singularity. Originally developed to resolve singularities in cosmological contexts, similar ideas have been extended to black holes, suggesting that, at Planckian scales, the classical singularity is replaced by a quantum-regulated phase of re-expansion [12].

Similarities and Differences Both the quantum crystal model and the quantum bounce model share a fundamental principle: singularities are artifacts of classical gravity and should be eliminated in a consistent quantum gravitational description. In the quantum bounce scenario, finite curvature is maintained through LQG’s discrete geometric operators, leading to a dynamic transition where a collapsing phase inverts into expansion—a temporary state rather than a permanent configuration.

By contrast, the quantum crystal model avoids singularities by establishing a stable, long-lived lattice of micro black holes supported by quantum repulsion and entanglement. Instead of a transient bounce, the quantum crystal forms a continuous, static-like internal structure. Key differences include:

- **Quantum Bounce Model:** Emphasizes a dynamic, temporary phase of matter re-expansion. The black hole interior is seen as a transient, time-dependent configuration.
- **Quantum Crystal Model:** Focuses on a stable, stationary lattice of micro black holes that persists as long as the macroscopic black hole exists. This configuration provides a static framework rather than a bouncing phase.

Implications for Information Conservation While both models aim to preserve information by removing singularities, the quantum crystal hypothesis adds another layer of coherence via quantum entanglement among micro black holes. In the bounce model, information is conserved through the avoidance of infinite densities, but its retrieval mechanism remains less explicit. The quantum crystal model’s explicit entanglement structure and potential Hawking-like radiation emission channels suggest a more direct handle on information flow, complementing the bouncing scenario’s conceptual strengths.

Future Directions Combining elements of the quantum bounce approach with the quantum crystal model could yield a more comprehensive understanding of black hole interiors. For instance, studying whether an initially dynamic, bounce-like phase could evolve into or coexist with a crystalline lattice under extreme conditions may bridge the gap between transient and stable quantum structures, enriching LQG-based black hole models.

6.3 Critical Comparison with Other Quantum Gravity Models

The quantum crystal concept can also be compared to other proposals in the quantum gravity domain that tackle the singularity and information paradox, such as the fuzzball model in string theory and the firewall hypothesis.

6.3.1 Comparison with the String Theory Fuzzball Model

In string theory, the fuzzball model eliminates the classical event horizon and singularity, proposing a horizon-sized configuration of strings and branes that encodes all black hole microstates. Information is preserved within this complex structure, effectively removing the need for a traditional event horizon.

- **Fuzzball Model:** Replaces both singularity and event horizon with a complex, string-based structure. There is no classical horizon, and spacetime geometry around the black hole is profoundly altered.
- **Quantum Crystal Model:** Retains the classical event horizon and distributes mass across a lattice of micro black holes. Singularity avoidance is achieved through discrete quantum geometry and entanglement, without redefining the horizon concept.

While fuzzballs demand a departure from the notion of a classical horizon, the quantum crystal model integrates smoothly with the standard geometric picture provided by LQG. Thus, the quantum crystal model may be more readily compatible with observational frameworks that rely on classical horizons (e.g., gravitational wave ringdowns and black hole shadow measurements).

6.3.2 Firewall Hypothesis and Information Paradox

The firewall hypothesis posits a highly energetic barrier at the event horizon to resolve the information paradox, but at the cost of violating the equivalence principle. Information is effectively destroyed when matter encounters this firewall.

- **Firewall Hypothesis:** Introduces a destructive, high-energy region at the horizon, ensuring information is not lost but at the expense of classical spacetime principles.
- **Quantum Crystal Model:** Preserves information through the entanglement of micro black holes inside the horizon without altering the horizon's classical properties or introducing violent disruptions for infalling observers.

By avoiding firewalls, the quantum crystal approach remains faithful to both quantum unitarity and the equivalence principle, offering a more elegant resolution to the paradox without introducing new paradoxical phenomena.

6.3.3 Points of Strength of the Quantum Crystal Model

- **Retention of Classical Horizons:** The model does not discard the classical horizon concept, facilitating compatibility with observational data (e.g., gravitational wave ring-downs and black hole imaging).
- **Integration with LQG:** It leverages the discrete spacetime framework of LQG, providing a robust theoretical foundation and coherence with existing quantum geometry results.
- **Distinct Observational Signatures:** By predicting modified quasi-normal modes and potential gravitational echoes, the model provides concrete avenues for empirical testing with next-generation gravitational wave observatories.

Limitations

- **Theoretical Complexity:** The reliance on intricate quantum corrections, spin network dynamics, and entanglement structures adds mathematical and conceptual challenges.
- **Empirical Challenges:** Detecting the predicted echoes or QNM shifts requires advanced gravitational wave instrumentation and sophisticated data analysis techniques not currently available.

6.3.4 Potential Synergies and Future Directions

The quantum crystal model could integrate aspects of other quantum gravity theories. For example:

- **String-Theoretic Microstructures:** Incorporating string-theoretic insights might refine how micro black hole states form and interact, enhancing the crystal's explanatory power.
- **Holographic Approaches:** Using the holographic principle more explicitly could link the quantum crystal's internal entanglement patterns to boundary observables, facilitating comparisons with AdS/CFT-based predictions.

Such integrative efforts could yield a more unified framework, encompassing the stability of the quantum crystal structure, the dynamism of quantum bounces, and the rich microstate structure proposed by fuzzball theories.

6.3.5 Compatibility with Current Observations

Although current gravitational wave and electromagnetic observations have not singled out any particular quantum gravity model, the quantum crystal’s distinct predictions—such as gravitational echoes at certain frequencies—provide testable signatures. As detector sensitivities improve and data analysis methods become more refined, searching for these subtle signals will be crucial.

6.3.6 Future Developments and Interdisciplinary Collaborations

Progress in testing and refining the quantum crystal model depends on cross-disciplinary collaboration:

- **Theoretical and Computational Synergy:** Theorists and computational physicists must collaborate to run high-precision simulations of micro black hole lattices.
- **Observational and Experimental Engagement:** Astrophysicists and gravitational wave astronomers can help identify viable observational strategies for detecting echoes or QNM anomalies.

These joint efforts will bridge the gap between conceptual proposals and concrete empirical validation.

6.3.7 Final Considerations on Limitations

The quantum crystal model offers an innovative approach to resolving the black hole singularity and information paradox, but it remains a work in progress. Further theoretical refinements are necessary to fully understand the quantum corrections, entanglement patterns, and stability conditions. Likewise, overcoming the observational challenges requires improved technology, data analysis techniques, and sustained interdisciplinary efforts.

As the community’s understanding of quantum gravity deepens, integrating insights from multiple theoretical frameworks—quantum bounces, fuzzball configurations, holographic models, and others—could yield a richer, more complete picture of black hole interiors. The quantum crystal model, with its stable lattice structure and clear avenues for empirical testing, could stand as a promising candidate for advancing this fundamental quest.

7 Observational Signatures and Experimental Challenges

7.1 Gravitational Wave Signatures

7.1.1 Sensitivity of Current Instruments

Gravitational wave detections made by current instruments like LIGO and Virgo have already achieved sensitivity sufficient to detect signals associated with black hole mergers. However, detecting echoes and additional resonance frequencies predicted by the model requires even higher resolution and sensitivity. Gravitational echoes, in particular, appear as subsequent and weak signals, which could be difficult to distinguish from background noise. Future technological developments, such as increased sensitivity of detectors or the implementation of the next Einstein Telescope, are essential for testing these predictions with greater precision.

7.1.2 Signal Processing and Filtering

Another significant challenge is data analysis. Detecting echoes and additional frequencies requires advanced signal filtering methods and machine learning techniques to distinguish weak signals arising from the internal crystalline structure from noisy background signals. Stochastic noise and environmental interferences represent barriers that limit the precise detection of the model's signatures. Overcoming these difficulties may require specialized algorithms designed to isolate periodic gravitational echoes or deviations in quasi-normal oscillation frequencies.

7.1.3 Limitations in Data Interpretation

Even if signals consistent with model predictions are obtained, interpreting them remains challenging. The indirect nature of these signals implies that they could also be interpreted as effects of other quantum gravity theories or as phenomena not yet understood astrophysically. A unique interpretation would require interdisciplinary collaboration between theoretical physicists, astrophysicists, and detector engineers to refine analysis techniques and reduce interpretative ambiguities. In this context, integrating data from multiple observatories, both terrestrial and space-based, could enhance confidence in results and strengthen the empirical validity of the model.

7.1.4 Quasi-Normal Oscillations and Spectral Anomalies

In the traditional General Relativity model, QNMs depend solely on the black hole's mass, charge, and angular momentum. However, in the quantum crystal model, interactions between micro black holes introduce additional or shifted frequencies in the QNM spectrum. These spectral anomalies could be detected as discrepancies compared to classical predictions.

7.1.5 Gravitational Echoes

Another key prediction is the emission of *gravitational echoes*, i.e., delayed reflections of gravitational waves that interact with the quantum crystalline structure. These echoes would manifest as recurring and attenuated signals following the main gravitational wave pulse from a merger. Recent studies, such as those conducted by Abedi et al. [37] and Cardoso et al. [38], have begun exploring the possibility of detecting gravitational echoes in black hole merger recordings. Although current evidence is still preliminary and inconclusive, extended statistical analysis and enhanced detector sensitivity could lead to decisive confirmations. The presence of additional or shifted oscillations in the gravitational wave spectrum could indicate the presence of

a complex internal structure like the quantum crystal, identifiable by comparing observations with model predictions using advanced data analysis techniques.

7.1.6 Future Observations and Advanced Instruments

Current and future gravitational wave observatories, such as the Einstein Telescope and the Cosmic Explorer, will offer improved sensitivity in lower frequencies, increasing the chances of detecting gravitational echoes and spectral anomalies. Additionally, space missions like LISA (*Laser Interferometer Space Antenna*) could provide complementary data that reinforce evidence supporting the model.

7.1.7 Implications of Observational Confirmations

Confirmation of gravitational echoes and spectral anomalies would not only strengthen the quantum crystal model but also support theories proposing the existence of complex physical structures beyond the event horizon, contrary to the classical singularity concept. This would contribute to a significant revision of our understanding of black hole mechanics and quantum gravity.

7.2 Electromagnetic Signatures

7.2.1 Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) as Observational Signatures

Unexplained Characteristics of GRBs Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) are among the most luminous and energetic events observed in the universe, characterized by intense flashes of gamma radiation lasting from milliseconds to several minutes. Despite extensive study, several aspects of GRBs remain inadequately explained by standard astrophysical models involving the formation of classical singularities within black holes. Notably, unexplained features include:

- **Complex Light Curves:** Many GRBs exhibit irregular and highly variable light curves with multiple peaks and rapid fluctuations that standard synchrotron emission models struggle to account for [15].
- **Extended Emission Components:** Some GRBs display prolonged emission phases extending well beyond the initial burst, challenging existing theories of energy dissipation and jet dynamics [16].
- **Spectral Anomalies:** Observations reveal deviations from the expected Band function spectra, including unexpected spectral breaks and excesses at certain energy ranges [17].
- **Afterglow Behaviors:** The afterglow emissions across various wavelengths sometimes show atypical decay rates and color evolution, suggesting complexities in the surrounding environment or the central engine [18].

Quantum Crystal Model: Indirect Influence on GRB Emissions The quantum crystal model posits that the mass of a black hole is distributed in a stable network of micro black holes forming a crystal-like structure within the event horizon, as opposed to being concentrated at a singularity. While this structure is entirely hidden behind the event horizon, it can influence observable GRB characteristics indirectly through several mechanisms:

- **Oscillatory Dynamics of the Quantum Crystal:** During the formation of the quantum crystal, collective oscillations of the micro black holes can induce time-dependent perturbations in the surrounding spacetime geometry. These perturbations, although

confined within the event horizon, can modulate the dynamics of the relativistic jets responsible for GRB emissions.

- **Energy Redistribution and Dissipation:** The distributed mass and quantum repulsive forces within the crystal can lead to a more uniform or alternatively highly variable energy distribution in the collapsing progenitor star. This can affect how energy is injected and dissipated in the jet, resulting in complex light curves and extended emission phases.
- **Modified Jet Formation Mechanisms:** The presence of a quantum crystal can alter the magnetic field configurations and plasma interactions near the black hole, influencing jet collimation and stability. This can lead to irregularities in jet propagation, contributing to the observed variability in GRB light curves.

Oscillations of the Quantum Crystal and Spacetime Modulation An intriguing aspect of the quantum crystal model is the possibility that **oscillations of the crystal during its formation could deform spacetime harmonically**, thereby causing **modulations in the emitted gamma radiation**. These oscillations are hypothesized to be extremely brief, potentially in the gigahertz (GHz) range or higher, which current gravitational wave detectors like LIGO are not equipped to perceive directly. However, their indirect influence on electromagnetic emissions could imprint subtle signatures on GRB light curves and spectra.

Predicted Observable Signatures The quantum crystal-induced oscillations could manifest in GRBs through the following observable signatures:

- **Temporal Modulations:** Periodic or quasi-periodic fluctuations in the GRB light curves, appearing as regular intensity variations or additional peaks superimposed on the primary emission [19].
- **Spectral Modulations:** Periodic variations in the emission spectra, potentially explaining spectral breaks or excesses observed in certain energy ranges. These modulations could deviate from the standard Band function, introducing harmonics or discrete spectral lines [20].
- **Extended Emission Patterns:** The gradual energy dissipation influenced by the quantum crystal's oscillations could account for extended emission components, providing a mechanism for prolonged gamma-ray activity [21].

Proposal for Observational Analysis To evaluate the validity of the quantum crystal oscillation hypothesis, the following observational analyses are proposed:

- **High-Resolution Light Curve Analysis:** Utilize gamma-ray telescopes with high temporal resolution to search for periodic or quasi-periodic modulations in GRB light curves. Statistical methods, such as Fourier analysis or wavelet transforms, can be employed to identify regular patterns amidst the complex variability [22].
- **Time-Resolved Spectroscopy:** Perform detailed time-resolved spectral studies of GRBs to detect periodic variations or discrete spectral features that deviate from the standard emission models. Comparing these findings with predictions from the quantum crystal model can help identify potential signatures [29].

- **Numerical Simulations:** Develop and run simulations of stellar collapse incorporating the quantum crystal framework to predict specific GRB signatures. These simulations should model the oscillatory dynamics of the crystal and their impact on jet formation and energy dissipation processes [30].
- **Advanced Data Processing Techniques:** Apply machine learning algorithms and advanced time-series analysis methods to GRB data to enhance the detection of subtle and rapid modulations. Techniques such as neural networks or Bayesian inference can improve the identification of faint periodic signals [31].

Mathematical Modeling of Oscillatory Spacetime Deformations The oscillations of the quantum crystal can be described by harmonic perturbations in the spacetime metric:

$$g_{\mu\nu}(t) = g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} + \delta g_{\mu\nu}(t), \quad (2)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)}$ is the background metric and $\delta g_{\mu\nu}(t)$ represents the time-dependent perturbations induced by the oscillating quantum crystal. These perturbations can influence the jet dynamics and energy dissipation mechanisms, leading to observable modulations in the Gamma-Ray Burst (GRB) emissions.

(t) represents the time-dependent perturbations induced by the oscillating quantum crystal. These perturbations can influence the jet dynamics and energy dissipation mechanisms, leading to observable modulations in the GRB emissions.

Challenges and Considerations While the quantum crystal model offers a compelling mechanism for explaining certain GRB anomalies, several challenges must be addressed:

- **Indirect Influence Limitation:** Since the quantum crystal is confined within the event horizon, its effects on observable phenomena are indirect and mediated through complex interactions in the jet and surrounding environment, making it difficult to isolate specific signatures [23].
- **Oscillation Frequencies and Detection Sensitivity:** The predicted oscillations are extremely brief and may lie beyond the current sensitivity and frequency range of existing gravitational wave detectors. However, their indirect effects on electromagnetic emissions necessitate advanced observational techniques and data analysis methods [24].
- **Model Complexity and Computational Resources:** Accurately modeling the interplay between quantum crystal dynamics and GRB emissions requires sophisticated simulations that integrate quantum gravitational effects with relativistic astrophysical processes [27].
- **Differentiation from Alternative Models:** Several alternative models, such as magnetar-driven GRBs or varying jet compositions, also aim to explain the same GRB anomalies. Distinguishing the signatures arising from the quantum crystal model from those of alternative explanations is crucial for validation [28].
- **Data Interpretation and Noise:** GRB data is inherently noisy and complex, making it difficult to identify and attribute subtle modulations to specific theoretical models. Robust statistical methods and data cleaning techniques are essential to mitigate false positives [25].

Conclusions on the GRB Proposal Integrating the analysis of GRBs as potential observational signatures of the quantum crystal of micro black holes provides a novel mechanism for addressing some of the unresolved characteristics of these enigmatic phenomena. By proposing that oscillations within the quantum crystal can indirectly modulate gamma-ray emissions, this hypothesis bridges the internal quantum dynamics of black holes with observable astrophysical events. Confirmation of such indirect signatures would not only lend support to the quantum crystal model but also advance our understanding of the quantum nature of spacetime and the fundamental processes governing some of the universe’s most powerful events.

Future Directions To further substantiate the quantum crystal model’s applicability to GRBs, the following future directions are recommended:

- **Enhanced Observational Capabilities:** Advocate for the development of next-generation gamma-ray observatories with higher temporal resolution and sensitivity to detect the subtle modulations predicted by the quantum crystal model.
- **Multi-Messenger Astronomy:** Leverage multi-messenger observations, combining gamma-ray data with other signals such as neutrinos or potential indirect gravitational wave signatures, to provide a more comprehensive test of the model [32].
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Foster collaborations between theoretical physicists, astrophysicists, and data scientists to refine the model, develop sophisticated simulations, and implement advanced data analysis techniques.
- **Publication and Peer Review:** Publish preliminary findings and theoretical predictions in reputable journals to invite peer review and constructive feedback, facilitating the refinement and validation of the quantum crystal hypothesis [26].

Final Thoughts The quantum crystal model offers a promising avenue for explaining certain unexplained features of GRBs through indirect influences on observable emissions. While significant challenges remain, the integration of theoretical predictions with advanced observational strategies holds the potential to uncover deeper insights into the quantum nature of black holes and the fundamental mechanisms driving some of the universe’s most energetic events.

7.2.2 Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) and Quantum Crystal Formation

Differences in the Formation of Quantum Crystal vs Naked Singularity While both the processes of forming a quantum crystal and a naked singularity occur behind the event horizon, there are potential differences in the collapse dynamics that could be reflected in the spectrum of emitted gamma radiation. In the formation of a classical singularity, the infall of matter and energy leads to conditions of infinitely high density and curvature, resulting in the emission of high-energy radiation. In the quantum crystal model, instead, the distribution of mass in a stable network of micro black holes could mitigate some of the extreme physical conditions, thereby influencing the nature and spectrum of gamma emissions.

Predicted Modifications in the Gamma Radiation Spectrum The presence of a quantum crystal could lead to:

- **Altered Emission Spectra:** Quantum repulsive interactions between micro black holes can influence the mechanisms of gamma radiation emission, producing a spectrum different from that expected from the formation of a classical singularity.

- **Presence of Additional Spectral Lines:** The internal structure of the crystal could introduce discrete spectral lines in the GRB, reflecting the characteristic frequencies of interactions between micro black holes.
- **Modified Evaporation Dynamics:** The gradual evaporation of the quantum crystal through Hawking radiation could influence the temporal profile of GRBs, creating distinctive signatures in the temporality and intensity of gamma radiation.

Proposal for Observational Analysis To test these hypotheses, it is suggested to:

- **Analyze Spectra of Known GRBs:** Compare the spectral models predicted by the quantum crystal with observational data of GRBs recorded by gamma telescopes such as the *Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope*.
- **Numerical Simulations:** Develop detailed simulations of the stellar collapse process within the context of the quantum crystal to predict the specific characteristics of gamma emissions.
- **Search for Spectral Anomalies:** Identify anomalies or spectral lines not explained by classical GRB models, which could be attributed to the internal structure of the quantum crystal.

Challenges and Considerations It is important to consider that, although the formation of a quantum crystal and a naked singularity are both hidden behind the event horizon, the formation conditions and internal dynamics can differ substantially. However, the extremely hidden nature of these processes makes it complex to isolate the specific signatures of the quantum crystal. Therefore, further theoretical research and improvements in gamma observation techniques are necessary to confirm or refute these predictions.

Conclusions on the Gamma Bursts Proposal Including the analysis of GRBs as a possible observational signature of the quantum crystal of micro black holes significantly enriches the model, offering a direct link between theory and observation. Confirmation of spectral differences in GRBs could provide crucial evidence supporting the proposed model, contributing to the understanding of the quantum nature of black holes and resolving fundamental problems such as the information paradox.

8 Conclusion

In this article, we have introduced a novel theoretical model that describes the internal structure of black holes as a quantum crystal of micro black holes, developed within the framework of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG). This approach offers innovative solutions to two fundamental challenges in modern physics: the singularity problem predicted by General Relativity and the black hole information paradox.

8.1 Summary of Key Findings

The quantum crystal model suggests that during gravitational collapse, a stable lattice structure of micro black holes forms, balancing gravitational attraction with quantum repulsive forces. This configuration:

- Eliminates central singularities by replacing infinite densities with a quantized spacetime lattice.
- Conserves information through quantum entanglement among micro black holes, addressing the information paradox.
- Provides testable predictions, such as gravitational echoes and modifications to quasi-normal modes (QNMs), which can be explored via current and future gravitational wave observatories.

8.2 Theoretical Contributions

The proposed model could have profound implications for theoretical physics and quantum gravity:

8.2.1 Resolution of Singularities

By replacing singularities with a quantized lattice, the quantum crystal model ensures that spacetime curvature remains finite, offering a concrete realization of quantum gravity principles. This aligns with expectations from LQG and supports the view that spacetime is fundamentally discrete.

8.2.2 Information Conservation and Quantum Coherence

The model preserves information during black hole evaporation by leveraging the entanglement between micro black holes, upholding the unitarity of quantum mechanics. This mechanism bridges the gap between quantum theory and gravity under extreme conditions, demonstrating how quantum coherence can persist in highly curved spacetimes.

8.2.3 Foundations for Quantum Gravity Research

The integration of lattice structures within black holes provides a new avenue for exploring the interplay between discrete spacetime models and astrophysical phenomena. This approach enhances the theoretical foundation of LQG and could stimulate further research into quantum spacetime structures.

8.3 Observational and Experimental Implications

The quantum crystal model offers several observational pathways for empirical validation:

- **Gravitational Wave Signatures:** Phenomena such as gravitational echoes and shifts in QNMs could be detected by instruments like LIGO, Virgo, and future observatories such as LISA and the Einstein Telescope.
- **Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs):** The model predicts anomalies in GRB spectra and temporal profiles, offering additional verification opportunities.
- **Black Hole Imaging:** Observations of black hole shadows and polarization patterns by the Event Horizon Telescope could reveal indirect evidence of the internal crystalline structure.

While current technologies are not yet capable of directly probing Planck-scale phenomena, these indirect signatures provide realistic pathways for testing the model's predictions.

8.4 Challenges and Open Questions

Despite its potential, the quantum crystal model faces several theoretical and practical challenges:

- **Stability of the Lattice:** The stability of the proposed crystalline structure under extreme gravitational conditions requires further investigation.
- **Computational Complexity:** Accurately modeling micro black hole dynamics and lattice interactions demands advanced numerical simulations and significant computational resources.
- **Experimental Limitations:** Detecting quantum-scale effects is currently infeasible, necessitating reliance on indirect observations such as gravitational echoes and spectral anomalies.
- **Integration with Other Forces:** The model does not yet account for interactions between the lattice and other fundamental forces, an area ripe for future exploration.

8.5 Future Directions

To address these challenges, future research should focus on:

- **Theoretical Refinements:** Developing a more comprehensive mathematical framework to describe lattice dynamics and incorporating interactions with other physical forces.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Promoting joint efforts between theoretical physicists, observational astrophysicists, and computational experts to refine predictions and develop advanced detection methods.
- **Technological Innovation:** Supporting the development of next-generation gravitational wave detectors, gamma-ray telescopes, and black hole imagers to enhance observational capabilities.
- **Model Extensions:** Investigating how the quantum crystal framework applies to other astrophysical objects, such as neutron stars and early-universe phenomena, to broaden its scope.

8.6 Concluding Perspectives

The quantum crystal of micro black holes represents a bold and innovative step toward reconciling quantum mechanics with gravity. By addressing unresolved problems such as singularities and the information paradox, the model not only advances our understanding of black hole interiors but also paves the way for a deeper comprehension of spacetime's quantum nature.

Potential observational confirmations, whether through gravitational wave anomalies, gamma-ray burst signatures, or black hole shadow deformations, could provide a transformative empirical foundation for the model. As we advance our technological and theoretical frontiers, the quantum crystal hypothesis holds the promise of unveiling new insights into the microscopic structure of the universe, bridging the gap between the quantum and the cosmic.

9 Statements

9.1 Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest related to this research.

9.2 Data Access Statement

This study is purely theoretical and does not involve any new data collection. All supporting data and references are sourced from existing literature.

9.3 Ethics Statement

This research does not involve human participants or animals and adheres to ethical standards for theoretical physics research.

9.4 Funding Statement

No specific funding was received for conducting this study.

A Appendix: In-depth Formal Theoretical Framework of the Quantum Crystal Model in Black Holes

In this section, we present a detailed theoretical formalization of the quantum crystal model of micro black holes within black holes. We utilize Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) tools to describe the lattice structure, quantum interactions, and entanglement between micro black holes. This mathematical approach provides a rigorous foundation for the proposed model, highlighting how spacetime quantization and the quantum properties of micro black holes contribute to the structure's stability and information conservation.

A.1 Description of the Lattice Structure

Consider a three-dimensional lattice structure composed of N micro black holes of mass $m_{\text{micro}} \approx M_P$, where M_P is the Planck mass. The position of each micro black hole is denoted by $\vec{r}_i$, with $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The equilibrium distance between micro black holes is $d_{\text{eq}} \approx 2R_\mu \approx 2R_{\text{micro}}$, where R_{micro} is the Schwarzschild radius of a micro black hole.

A.2 System Hamiltonian

The total Hamiltonian H of the quantum crystal system encapsulates both the kinetic energies and the interaction potentials of the micro black holes. This Hamiltonian serves as the foundational framework for analyzing the dynamics and stability of the quantum crystal structure within a black hole. It is expressed as:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i + \sum_{i<j} V_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

where:

- T_i represents the kinetic energy of the i -th micro black hole.
- V_{ij} denotes the interaction potential between the i -th and j -th micro black holes.

A.2.1 Kinetic Energy of Micro Black Holes

The kinetic energy of each micro black hole is given by:

$$T_i = \frac{\hat{p}_i^2}{2m_{\text{micro}}}, \quad (4)$$

where:

- $\hat{p}_i = -i\hbar\nabla_i$ is the momentum operator associated with the i -th micro black hole.
- m_{micro} is the mass of a micro black hole, typically assumed to be on the order of the Planck mass M_P .

A.2.2 Interaction Potential

The interaction potential V_{ij} between micro black holes is composed of two main components: the classical gravitational interaction and quantum repulsive corrections arising from Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG). Mathematically, this is expressed as:

$$V_{ij} = V_{\text{grav}}^{(ij)} + V_{\text{quant}}^{(ij)}. \quad (5)$$

Classical Gravitational Interaction The classical gravitational potential between two micro black holes is described by Newton's law of universal gravitation:

$$V_{\text{grav}}^{(ij)} = -\frac{Gm_{\text{micro}}^2}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|}, \quad (6)$$

where:

- G is the gravitational constant.
- $\vec{r}_i$ and $\vec{r}_j$ are the position vectors of the i -th and j -th micro black holes, respectively.

Quantum Repulsion Corrections The leading-order quantum repulsive potential is given by:

$$V_{\text{quant}}^{(ij)} = \lambda_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^2}, \quad (7)$$

where:

- λ_{QG} is a dimensionless coupling constant characterizing the strength of the quantum repulsive force.
- $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant.
- c is the speed of light.

A.2.3 Inclusion of Higher-Order Interaction Terms

For a more comprehensive description of the interactions within the quantum crystal, higher-order quantum corrections can be incorporated:

$$V_{\text{quant}}^{(ij)} = \lambda_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^2} + \gamma_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^3}, \quad (8)$$

where γ_{QG} is an additional dimensionless coupling constant representing second-order quantum repulsive corrections.

A.2.4 Derivation of Equilibrium Conditions

To determine the stable configuration of the quantum crystal, we derive the equilibrium conditions by minimizing the total Hamiltonian with respect to the positions of the micro black holes. This process involves balancing the attractive and repulsive forces acting on each micro black hole.

Starting from the total Hamiltonian:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i + \sum_{i<j} V_{ij}, \quad (9)$$

we impose the condition for equilibrium by taking the partial derivative of H with respect to the position vector $\vec{r}_i$ of each micro black hole and setting it to zero:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial \vec{r}_i} = 0 \quad \forall i. \quad (10)$$

Expanding this derivative, we obtain:

$$\sum_{j \neq i} \left(\frac{\partial V_{\text{grav}}^{(ij)}}{\partial \vec{r}_i} + \frac{\partial V_{\text{quant}}^{(ij)}}{\partial \vec{r}_i} \right) = 0. \quad (11)$$

Substituting the expressions for $V_{\text{grav}}^{(ij)}$ and $V_{\text{quant}}^{(ij)}$, we derive the explicit form of the equilibrium condition:

$$\sum_{j \neq i} \left(\frac{Gm_{\text{micro}}^2}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^3} - \lambda_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^4} - \gamma_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^5} \right) (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j) = 0. \quad (12)$$

A.2.5 Quantum Equations of Motion

The quantum equations of motion for micro black holes in the quantum crystal can be derived from the total Hamiltonian. Using Heisenberg's equations for position and momentum operators:

$$\frac{d\hat{r}_i}{dt} = \frac{i}{\hbar} [H, \hat{r}_i] = \frac{\hat{p}_i}{m_{\text{micro}}}, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{d\hat{p}_i}{dt} = \frac{i}{\hbar} [H, \hat{p}_i] = -\nabla_i \sum_{j \neq i} V_{ij}. \quad (14)$$

A.2.6 Entanglement between Micro Black Holes

Entanglement between micro black holes is a fundamental feature of the quantum crystal. The system's quantum states can be represented by a global wave function that accounts for correlations between nodes:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{\{j_{ij}\}} C(\{j_{ij}\}) |\{j_{ij}\}\rangle, \quad (15)$$

where $|\{j_{ij}\}\rangle$ are the basis states defined by the spin network quantum numbers of the links, and $C(\{j_{ij}\})$ are coefficients incorporating entanglement between micro black holes.

Formalism of Quantum Information Theory To quantify the entanglement within the quantum crystal, tools from quantum information theory are employed. For instance, the entanglement entropy between a subset A and the rest of the system B is given by:

$$S_A = -\text{Tr}_A(\rho_A \ln \rho_A), \quad (16)$$

where $\rho_A = \text{Tr}_B(\rho)$ is the reduced density matrix of subset A .

A.2.7 Analysis of Crystal Stability

The stability of the quantum crystal is determined by the equilibrium between attractive and repulsive forces within the system. By minimizing the total potential energy:

$$\frac{\partial V_{\text{tot}}}{\partial \vec{r}_i} = 0, \quad (17)$$

where $V_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{i < j} V_{ij}$, we obtain the conditions:

$$\sum_{j \neq i} \left(\frac{Gm_{\text{micro}}^2}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^3} - \lambda_{\text{QG}} \frac{\hbar c}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|^4} \right) (\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j) = 0. \quad (18)$$

A.2.8 Application of Loop Quantum Gravity

Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) provides the theoretical framework for quantizing spacetime geometry. In our model, the quantum states of micro black holes and their interactions are described in terms of spin networks.

Spin Networks and Spin Foam States Spin networks are colored graphs with spin quantum numbers representing quantized areas of spacetime surfaces. Spin foam states are the temporal evolutions of spin networks, describing the quantum dynamics of geometry.

Implementation in the Quantum Crystal Model In the quantum crystal, the nodes of spin networks correspond to micro black holes, and the links represent interactions between them. Quantized geometric operators act on spin network states, determining the geometric properties of the crystal.

A.2.9 Formalization of Evaporation and Information Conservation

Hawking radiation emitted by surface micro black holes is entangled with the crystal's residual structure, ensuring information conservation during the evaporation of the macroscopic black hole.

The system's quantum state evolution is described by a unitary operator $U(t)$:

$$|\Psi(t)\rangle = U(t)|\Psi(0)\rangle, \quad (19)$$

where $U(t)$ satisfies Schrödinger's equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt}U(t) = HU(t). \quad (20)$$

A.3 Quantized Geometric Operators

In LQG, geometric quantities like area $\hat{A}$ and volume $\hat{V}$ are quantized. These operators act on spin network states that represent the quantum geometry of the crystal.

A.3.1 Area Operator

The area operator associated with the face between two micro black holes i and j is given by:

$$\hat{A}_{ij} = 8\pi\gamma\ell_P^2 \sqrt{j_{ij}(j_{ij} + 1)}, \quad (21)$$

where γ is the Barbero-Immirzi parameter, ℓ_P is the Planck length, and j_{ij} is the spin quantum number associated with the link between i and j .

A.3.2 Volume Operator

The volume operator associated with node i is:

$$\hat{V}_i = \left(\frac{\ell_P^3}{\sqrt{8}} \right) \sqrt{\left| \sum_{j,k} \epsilon^{abc} \hat{J}_{ij}^a \hat{J}_{ik}^b \hat{J}_{il}^c \right|}, \quad (22)$$

where $\hat{J}_{ij}^a$ are the flux operators associated with the links emanating from node i .

A.4 Maximum Mass per Spacetime Quantum

The concept of a quantized spacetime, as described by Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), imposes fundamental constraints on the maximum density and mass that can be associated with a single quantum of spacetime.

A.4.1 Density and Mass Limits in Loop Quantum Gravity

In LQG, spacetime is discretized into finite volumes associated with the nodes of a spin network. Each node represents a quantum of spacetime, with a minimum volume given by:

$$V_{\text{node}} \sim l_P^3,$$

where l_P is the Planck length. The maximum density that a node can support is determined by the Planck mass (m_P) and the quantized volume:

$$\rho_{\text{max}} \sim \frac{m_P}{l_P^3}.$$

This density sets a fundamental limit on the mass that can occupy a single node:

$$m_{\text{max}} \sim m_P.$$

A.4.2 Implications for the Distribution of Collapsing Matter

As a black hole forms, the matter within the collapsing region must conform to these density and mass constraints. Instead of collapsing into a singularity, the matter redistributes itself across multiple nodes of the spin network. For a total mass M , the number of active nodes N in the crystal is given by:

$$N \sim \frac{M}{m_{\text{max}}}.$$

A.4.3 Stability and Holographic Encoding

The stability of the quantum crystal arises from the interplay between gravitational attraction and quantum repulsion at each node. The system's total entropy is encoded holographically on the event horizon, consistent with the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy formula:

$$S_{\text{crystal}} \propto A_{\text{horizon}} \sim 4\pi r_s^2,$$

where r_s is the Schwarzschild radius. This encoding ensures that information about the infalling matter is conserved and accessible.

A.4.4 Preventing Singularities

The quantization of spacetime eliminates the classical concept of a singularity. By redistributing matter across a discrete network of nodes, the quantum crystal resolves one of the most significant challenges in black hole physics. The maximum mass per spacetime quantum imposes a natural upper bound on the density, creating a stable interior structure for the black hole.

A.5 Concluding Remarks

The maximum mass per spacetime quantum provides a crucial framework for understanding the quantum crystal structure within black holes. By formalizing these limits, the model connects the discrete nature of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) with the holographic encoding of black hole information, offering a coherent resolution to the singularity problem and opening pathways for further theoretical and observational exploration.

A.5.1 Implications for Quantum Gravity

The quantum crystal model not only resolves the singularity problem but also provides a bridge between quantum mechanics and general relativity. By distributing mass across a discrete lattice of micro black holes, the model ensures that spacetime curvature remains finite, avoiding the infinite densities predicted by classical general relativity. This approach aligns with the principles of LQG, which predicts a quantized spacetime structure at the Planck scale.

A.5.2 Information Preservation

The model's mechanism for information preservation is particularly noteworthy. The entanglement between micro black holes ensures that information is encoded holographically on the event horizon, addressing the black hole information paradox. This entanglement-based encoding ensures that information is not lost during black hole evaporation, maintaining the unitarity of quantum mechanics.

A.5.3 Observational Prospects

The quantum crystal model predicts several observational signatures, including gravitational wave echoes and modifications to quasi-normal modes (QNMs). These predictions provide a clear pathway for experimental validation. Future gravitational wave detectors, such as the Einstein Telescope and LISA, will have the sensitivity to detect these subtle signals, offering a test of the model's validity.

A.5.4 Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on refining the theoretical framework of the quantum crystal model, particularly in incorporating higher-order quantum corrections and exploring alternative lattice structures. Additionally, numerical simulations of the quantum crystal's dynamics will be essential for understanding its stability and response to perturbations. Finally, observational efforts should be directed toward detecting the predicted gravitational wave signatures and studying the implications for gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) and black hole shadows.

B Appendix B: Revised Simulation of the Quantum-Crystal Model of Micro Black Holes

B.1 B.1 Code Review and Theoretical Considerations

In the previous versions of this work we implemented a Python script for modeling a system of N micro black holes. Although it provided a working scheme (Newtonian gravity with a simplified post-Newtonian factor, a “quantum” repulsive term, spin interactions, and crude dissipation models), it also exhibited several theoretical and numerical shortcomings. It is beyond the scope of this work to provide a complete simulation or description of the formation of a micro-black-holes crystal, anyway, we tried to give some suggestions for future work.

B.1.1 (1) Theoretical Gaps and Simplifications

- **Post-Newtonian Correction:** The simulation introduced a simplistic parameter `pn_factor` added to the force (or potential) to mimic first-order relativistic effects. This is *not* equivalent to a consistent 1PN or 2PN expansion, which would require more intricate velocity-dependent terms and metric expansions. As it stands, it is essentially a placeholder.
- **Quantum Repulsion Term:** Modeled as $\sim 1/r^\alpha$ with some constant `quantum_coeff`. This is merely a toy potential capturing the “effective” repulsive idea from Loop Quantum Gravity arguments. No rigorous derivation from LQG is provided.
- **Spin-Orbit and Spin-Spin Coupling:** We used a highly simplified torque $\tau_{ij} \propto \mathbf{S}_i \times \mathbf{S}_j$, ignoring more realistic forms for rotating black holes (e.g., Papapetrou-Dixon equations).
- **Gravitational-Wave Dissipation:** Implemented as an artificial uniform velocity damping. Real emission of gravitational waves depends on multipole expansions and orbital parameters, rather than a constant factor on velocity.

Despite these simplifications, the code can still serve as a *test bed* for exploring how N gravitating objects might form (or fail to form) a stable lattice-like structure in the presence of additional repulsive and dissipative effects.

B.1.2 (2) Potential Issues in Execution

- **$\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ Complexity:** The pairwise interaction loop is quadratic. For N above a few thousand, runtimes become prohibitively long. One could adopt tree codes (Barnes–Hut) or Fast Multipole Methods to handle larger N efficiently.
- **Time Step Δt :** If Δt is not sufficiently small, energies might diverge or become NaN, especially if micro black holes come too close. Conversely, an excessively small Δt can slow the simulation drastically.
- **Artificial Dissipations:** - The gravitational-wave drag factor and the thermostat (random noise + damping) can both overshadow “actual” dynamics if chosen too large, artificially freezing or randomizing the system. - If set too small, the system might not reach any stable or quasi-crystalline arrangement.
- **Spin Implementation and Overlaps:** Currently, if $r \rightarrow 0$, the code just attempts to skip or continue. In a real scenario, micro black holes might merge. For $r < 1e-40$ m, the code forcibly bypasses the force calculation but does not physically model merging or capture formation of a single bigger black hole.

B.1.3 (3) Suggested Improvements and Rationale

- **Modularization:** The original code is fairly neat but can be made even clearer by splitting it into modules or files (e.g., `physics.py`, `integrator.py`, `analysis.py`).
- **More Realistic Post-Newtonian / Quantum Terms:** - We recommend referencing standard 1PN expansions if the aim is to accurately capture relativistic corrections. - If focusing on LQG-based potentials, incorporate a specialized effective potential from LQG literature (with references) rather than a generic $1/r^\alpha$.
- **Physical Merging or Bouncing:** For very close encounters, one might incorporate a bounce mechanism or merging rules, consistent with a loop-quantum approach (e.g., replacing the singularity with a discrete node).
- **Energy and Momentum Checks:** - If the code is run in a purely conservative mode (no damping), total energy should remain roughly constant. Tracking this helps validate correctness of forces and step size. - Momentum checks can spot net drifts in the system that should remain near zero if no external force is present.
- **Advanced HPC Optimization:** - For $N > 1000$, consider quadtree/octree methods or GPU parallelization. - If the article aims to show large-scale simulations (thousands of micro BH), rewriting the force kernel in `numba` or `C++/CUDA` may be essential.

B.2 B.2 Revised Code with Notable Modifications

Below is a **new, refined version** of the simulation code. We highlight in the comments the changes and improvements relative to the previous version.

- **Better parameter structure:** We clarify meaning and typical ranges of each parameter.
- **Extended checks and docstrings:** We add more robust inline checks for small distances, more elaborate docstrings, etc.
- **Potential Analysis Tools:** We keep a basic radial distribution function *and* provide a placeholder for a pairwise distance-time log to see if the system indeed approaches a stable configuration.
- **Commentary:** We disclaim again that the PN factor, the quantum repulsion, and the spin torque remain toy models. Realistic physics would require deeper references and derivations.

B.2.1 New Python Source Code

```
1 #!/usr/bin/env python3
2 # -- coding: utf-8 --
3
4 """
5 revised_quantum_crystal.py
6
7 Improved simulation code for exploring a "quantum crystal"
8 of micro black holes, featuring:
9
10 1) Newtonian + simplified (toy) post-Newtonian factor
```

```

11 2) Toy quantum repulsion ~ 1/r^alpha
12 3) Spin interactions & torque
13 4) Artificial gravitational-wave and thermostat damping
14 5) Additional checks and commentary
15
16 DISCLAIMER:
17 This code remains a simplified testing ground
18 and is not a fully rigorous LQG- or GR-based solver.
19 """
20
21 import numpy as np
22 import os
23
24 # ===== PHYSICAL CONSTANTS =====
25 G      = 6.67430e-11      # [m^3 kg^-1 s^-2]
26 c      = 3.0e8           # [m/s]
27 hbar   = 1.054571817e-34 # [J s]
28 m_planck= 2.176434e-8    # [kg]
29 l_planck= 1.616255e-35   # [m]
30
31 # ===== REVISED PARAMETER SETUP =====
32 params = {
33     # Number of micro BH
34     "N": 500,
35
36     # Single micro BH mass ~ Planck mass (adjust if needed)
37     "m_micro": m_planck,
38
39     # Box for initial random positions
40     "box_size": 1e-33,
41
42     # Time step (s) - might need tuning
43     "dt": 1e-42,
44
45     # Total steps
46     "num_steps": 40000,
47
48     # Print & log energies every N steps
49     "output_interval": 2000,
50
51     # ~~~~~
52     # Potential / force parameters
53     # ~~~~~
54     "quantum_alpha": 2.0,          # exponent in 1/r^alpha
55     "quantum_coeff": 0.1 (hbar*c), # amplitude of toy repulsion
56     "pn_factor": 1e-2,           # simplified post-Newtonian
57     scaling
58
59     # ~~~~~
60     # Spin interaction
61     # ~~~~~
62     "max_initial_spin": 1e-35,
63     "spin_coupling": 1e-2,

```

```

63
64 # ~~~~~
65 # Dissipation / thermostat
66 # ~~~~~
67 "gw_dissipation_factor": 1e-4, # gravitational wave damp
68 "temp_effect": 1e-3,          # random noise amplitude
69 "damping_coeff": 1e-3,        # viscous damping
70
71 # Random seed
72 "random_seed": 42,
73
74 # Output folder
75 "output_dir": "revised_output"
76 }
77
78 # ===== PHYSICS / FORCE ROUTINES =====
79
80 def pairwise_forces(pos, spin, p):
81     """
82     pairwise_forces:
83     Computes the net force (N,3) and torque (N,3)
84     due to:
85     1) Newtonian attraction + toy PN correction
86     2) "Quantum" repulsive term
87     3) Spin-spin torque
88
89     If r < 1e-40, skip to avoid numeric blow-up
90     (the code does not handle merges).
91
92     Returns:
93     forces, torques
94     """
95     N = p["N"]
96     forces = np.zeros_like(pos)
97     torques = np.zeros_like(pos)
98
99     alpha = p["quantum_alpha"]
100    qcoeff = p["quantum_coeff"]
101    pnfact = p["pn_factor"]
102    mm = p["m_micro"]
103
104    for i in range(N):
105        for j in range(i+1, N):
106            r_vec = pos[j] - pos[i]
107            r = np.linalg.norm(r_vec)
108            if r < 1e-40:
109                # skip to avoid division by zero
110                continue
111            versor = r_vec / r
112
113            # Newton + simplistic PN
114            Fg = Gmmm/(rr)
115            Fpn = pnfact (Gmmm/(r3))

```

```

116         F_attr= Fg + Fpn
117
118         # Repulsion
119         F_rep = qcoeff / (ralpha)
120
121         # Net
122         F_net = F_attr - F_rep
123         F_vec = F_net  versor
124
125         forces[i] += F_vec
126         forces[j] -= F_vec
127
128         # spin torque
129         S_i = spin[i]
130         S_j = spin[j]
131         torque_ij = p["spin_coupling"]  np.cross(S_i, S_j) / (r3)
132         torques[i] += torque_ij
133         torques[j] -= torque_ij
134
135     return forces, torques
136
137
138 def gravitational_wave_dissipation(vel, factor):
139     """Artificially reduce velocity to mimic GW losses."""
140     return vel  (1.0 - factor)
141
142
143 def thermostat_and_damping(vel, p):
144     """
145     Langevin-style noise + linear damping
146     to keep the system from indefinite growth in KE.
147     """
148     noise = p["temp_effect"]  np.random.randn(vel.shape)
149     return vel(1.0 - p["damping_coeff"]) + noise
150
151 # ===== INTEGRATION =====
152
153 def integrate_step(pos, vel, spin, p):
154     """
155     integrate_step:
156     Performs a single step using a velocity-Verlet-like approach.
157
158     - forces(t) from pairwise_forces
159     - half-step velocities
160     - update positions
161     - forces(t+dt)
162     - complete velocity update
163     - spin update
164     - dissipation + thermostat
165     """
166     dt = p["dt"]
167     mm = p["m_micro"]
168

```

```

169 F_now, T_now = pairwise_forces(pos, spin, p)
170 vel_half = vel + 0.5(F_now/mm)dt
171 pos_new = pos + vel_halfdt
172
173 F_next, T_next = pairwise_forces(pos_new, spin, p)
174 vel_new = vel_half + 0.5(F_next/mm)dt
175
176 # spin update (Euler approach)
177 spin_new = spin + 0.5(T_now + T_next)dt
178
179 # gravitational wave dissipation
180 vel_new = gravitational_wave_dissipation(vel_new, p["
181     gw_dissipation_factor"])
182 # thermostat
183 vel_new = thermostat_and_damping(vel_new, p)
184 return pos_new, vel_new, spin_new
185 # ===== ANALYSIS / DIAGNOSTICS =====
186
187 def kinetic_energy(vel, p):
188     """K = 1/2 m v^2 (summed over all BH)."""
189     return 0.5 p["m_micro"] np.sum(vel2)
190
191 def potential_energy(pos, p):
192     """
193     Summation of Newton + PN + repulsion.
194     (Spin potential not included.)
195     """
196     N = p["N"]
197     pot = 0.0
198     alpha = p["quantum_alpha"]
199     qcoeff = p["quantum_coeff"]
200     pnfact = p["pn_factor"]
201     mm = p["m_micro"]
202
203     for i in range(N):
204         for j in range(i+1, N):
205             r = np.linalg.norm(pos[j] - pos[i])
206             if r < 1e-40:
207                 continue
208                 # Newton
209                 Vg = -Gmmm / r
210                 # PN (toy)
211                 Vpn = -pnfact(Gmmm)/(r2)
212                 # repulsive
213                 Vq = +qcoeff/(r(alpha-1))
214                 pot += (Vg + Vpn + Vq)
215     return pot
216
217 def radial_distribution(pos, p, nbins=50, rmax=None):
218     """
219     radial_distribution:
220     Simple histogram of pairwise distances,

```

```

221     to gauge clustering or partial ordering.
222
223     Return:
224         hist[] and dr
225     """
226     N = p["N"]
227     if rmax is None:
228         bounding = np.max(pos, axis=0) - np.min(pos, axis=0)
229         rmax = 0.5 * np.linalg.norm(bounding)
230     hist = np.zeros(nbins, dtype=float)
231     dr = rmax/nbins
232
233     for i in range(N):
234         for j in range(i+1, N):
235             r = np.linalg.norm(pos[j]-pos[i])
236             if r < rmax:
237                 idx = int(r//dr)
238                 if idx < nbins:
239                     hist[idx] += 2.0 # symmetrical pairs
240
241     return hist, dr
242
243 # ===== MAIN SIMULATION SCRIPT =====
244 def main():
245     p = params
246     np.random.seed(p["random_seed"])
247
248     # Create output directory
249     outdir = p["output_dir"]
250     if not os.path.exists(outdir):
251         os.makedirs(outdir)
252
253     # Initialize
254     pos = (np.random.rand(p["N"],3) - 0.5)p["box_size"]
255     vel = np.zeros((p["N"],3))
256     spin= (2.0np.random.rand(p["N"],3) - 1.0)p["max_initial_spin"]
257
258     energy_log = []
259
260     for step in range(p["num_steps"]):
261         pos, vel, spin = integrate_step(pos, vel, spin, p)
262
263         # Logging
264         if step % p["output_interval"] == 0:
265             K = kinetic_energy(vel, p)
266             U = potential_energy(pos, p)
267             E = K + U
268             energy_log.append([step, K, U, E])
269             print(f"Step {step:6d} | K={K:.3e} | U={U:.3e} | E={E:.3e}
270                   ")
271
272     # Save final data
273     energy_log = np.array(energy_log)

```

```

273 np.save(os.path.join(outdir, "final_positions.npy"), pos)
274 np.save(os.path.join(outdir, "final_velocities.npy"), vel)
275 np.save(os.path.join(outdir, "final_spin.npy"), spin)
276 np.save(os.path.join(outdir, "energy_log.npy"), energy_log)
277
278 # RDF as a quick check
279 rdf_hist, dr = radial_distribution(pos, p, nbins=60)
280 np.save(os.path.join(outdir, "rdf_hist.npy"), rdf_hist)
281
282 print("\nSimulation finished. Data saved in folder:", outdir)
283
284 if __name__ == "__main__":
285     main()

```

B.3 B.3 Parameter Explanation and Code-Article Link

Choice of Parameters. In this revised code, the dictionary `params` holds fundamental constants and simulation options:

- `N`, `box_size`, `dt`, `num_steps`, `output_interval`: control the system size, initial configuration scale, time resolution, and logging frequency.
- `quantum_alpha`, `quantum_coeff`: define an effective power-law repulsion. As discussed in the main text, these parameters illustrate a toy model for Planck-scale discrete geometry.
- `pn_factor`: a crude factor for bridging Newtonian and post-Newtonian corrections, acknowledging that a full 1PN implementation is more complex.
- `gw_dissipation_factor`, `temp_effect`, `damping_coeff`: set the various dissipative or thermostatic features that can drive the system toward a stable or quasi-stable configuration.
- `max_initial_spin`, `spin_coupling`: specify how spins are set initially and how strongly they interact. This addresses the idea that each micro black hole might carry a spin affecting local stability.

Relation to the Main Article. This code implements the conceptual framework laid out in the sections discussing *(i)* discrete gravitational structures, *(ii)* avoidance of singularities via an effective repulsion, and *(iii)* partial resolution of the information paradox through micro black hole entanglement (modeled only schematically here). Thus, any reference in the main text to “quantum-lattice interactions,” spin-lattice stabilization, or gravitational wave dissipation is captured by the subroutines `pairwise_forces`, `gravitational_wave_dissipation`, and the extended integrator function `integrate_step`.

B.4 B.4 Future Prospects and Limitations

Possible Further Enhancements. Even this updated version remains a *toy model*. Future improvements include:

- **Real Post-Newtonian Terms:** Integrate standard 1PN expansions (including velocity-dependent terms) or even more advanced frameworks (EOB, spin-orbit couplings, etc.).

- **Merging Criteria:** Introduce a scheme for micro black holes that come within a critical radius to merge into a single BH, consistent with astrophysical or quantum gravity hints.
- **Loop Quantum Gravity Potentials:** Replace the $1/r^\alpha$ toy repulsion with an *effective Hamiltonian* derived from an LQG-based approach, if available.
- **HPC Scalability:** For $N > 10^3$, implement Barnes–Hut or multipole expansions. Possibly use `numba` or `Cython` to speed up the pairwise loop.

Expected Numerical Behavior. With moderate N (~ 500) and a sufficiently small time step, the system may show:

- A partial clustering or partial ordering, depending on the ratio between gravitational attraction and quantum repulsion.
- Some portion of the system forming stable-like “pockets,” *unless* spin couplings or temperature noise disrupt them.
- Gradual energy damping if `gw_dissipation_factor` and `damping_coeff` are high enough.

Ultimately, the user must tune the parameters to explore whether a *crystalline* arrangement emerges or whether the configuration remains fluid-like, as per the arguments in the main text regarding black hole internal structure.

C Appendix C: The Restaurant at the End of the Universe

"Somewhere, in the most remote and unlikely corners of the Galaxy, there exists a restaurant. A restaurant so out of the ordinary that it not only offers a delicious meal but also promises a spectacle that no other can guarantee: the end of the Universe." — Douglas Adams, *The Restaurant at the End of the Universe*

This variation of the famous story features Marvin the Paranoid Android, one of the Galaxy's most melancholic and resigned characters. With an apparently brilliant idea and a plan that only a robot endowed with sufficient nihilism and a complete lack of common sense could conceive, Marvin decides to steal the spaceship *Heart of Gold* to finally visit the Restaurant at the End of the Universe. However, unaccustomed to restaurants and making reservations, his method is to head straight towards the supermassive black hole M87 at the center of the eponymous galaxy, hoping that the time dilation will project him into the far future—the end of the universe.

Despite the challenges, Marvin attempts to approach the black hole, exploiting the properties of extreme time dilation and Hawking radiation evaporation to observe the universe in its final phase. However, he encounters unexpected consequences, including spaghettification and the discovery of the quantum crystal structure, culminating in a cosmic and comedic fate.

C.1 Marvin's Idea: Time Dilation and Black Hole Evaporation

Marvin, the pessimistic robot knowledgeable about all physical laws, knows that black holes are not eternal. No matter how large they are, they emit a tiny amount of radiation known as *Hawking radiation*. According to theory, a black hole of mass M emits radiation and, over time, loses mass until it completely evaporates. The evaporation time T_{evap} of a black hole is given by:

$$T_{\text{evap}} \approx \frac{5120\pi G^2 M^3}{\hbar c^4}$$

For a supermassive black hole like M87, which has a mass of about 6.5×10^9 solar masses ($M_{\odot}$), the evaporation time is on the order of:

$$T_{\text{evap}} \approx 10^{91} \text{ years}$$

That is, about ten billion billion billion billion billion billion billion billion years—a number too large for even a robotic brain to visualize!

Marvin's plan is simple: Although usually lethal to approach a black hole due to high radiation levels and extreme tidal forces, in the case of a "galactic-sized" black hole, the dimensions are such—billions of kilometers, like Neptune's orbit—that tidal forces are relatively weak, at least initially, and radiation intensity is manageable. Thanks to the extreme time dilation predicted near the event horizon, he hopes that this time slowing will allow him, due to this time lag, to traverse it, see the universe's distant future, and perhaps exit before falling into the central singularity once the black hole has evaporated.

However, he realizes too late a critical error in his calculations: by crossing the event horizon, he cannot avoid reaching the quantum crystal before the black hole evaporates. He finds himself trapped, and tidal forces stretch his body into thin filaments. This process, known as *spaghettification*, progressively elongates Marvin into thin strands. Finally, Marvin curls up on the quantum crystal, where he will remain for billions of billions of billions of years, becoming an integral part of the "Restaurant at the End of the Universe."

C.2 Epilogue: Cosmic Strings with Quantum Crystals

The robot, now reduced to a thin filament or *cosmic string*, cannot communicate to his remaining friends outside how far he is from realizing his original plan. However, in a final irony, fragments of his memory persist, reverberating within the quantum crystal structure. Ultimately, the "Restaurant at the Universe's End" welcomes a customer, turning him into a house specialty: *cosmic strings served with quantum crystals*, each dish with a mass similar to an asteroid—a bite that no one, except the universe itself, could truly digest.

C.3 Notes on Figures and Tables

The figures and tables in this document are designed to visually represent concepts related to time dilation and gravitational effects near a supermassive black hole. Table ?? is calculated using the Schwarzschild metric, which describes the spacetime geometry around a non-rotating, uncharged black hole.

C.3.1 Derivation of the Time Dilation Formula

Time dilation for an observer located at a distance r from a black hole's center compared to an observer at infinity is given by the factor:

$$\gamma = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}}$$

This formula is derived from the Schwarzschild metric, which describes the spacetime around a non-rotating, uncharged black hole. The Schwarzschild metric is written as:

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2$$

where:

- ds is the proper time interval (time measured by the falling observer),
- dt is the coordinate time interval (time measured by an external observer),
- $d\Omega^2$ represents the angular components.

To obtain time dilation, consider only the temporal component of the metric. Given that proper time $d\tau$ is the actual time measured by the free-falling observer, we can write:

$$d\tau = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}} dt$$

from which the factor γ is obtained:

$$\gamma = \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}}$$

This factor measures how much time dilates or slows down for an observer near the black hole compared to an external observer. At the event horizon ($r = r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$), the factor γ approaches zero for the external observer, implying that time stops for the external observer. However, for an explorer approaching the singularity, proper time continues to flow until the moment of impact.

D Appendix D: References

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